

Effectiveness of Online Platforms for School Heads' Professional Development

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Abstract:

This descriptive research was conducted to assess the level of effectiveness of online platforms for School Heads' professional development. This investigation was carried out to 41 elementary and secondary school heads of Escalante City Division. Total enumeration was used in determining the participants of this investigation. The data of this study were obtained through utilizing a survey questionnaire as an instrument which was anchored to DepED Office Memorandum OUA Memo 00-0420-0042 and aligned to the standards set for professional development of school heads. The statistical tools that were employed in this study were frequency and percentage, mean and standard deviation. The statistical findings and analyses of this investigation revealed that there is no significant difference in the level of effectiveness of online platforms for School Heads' professional development in the Schools Division of Escalante City. Furthermore, results of this study show that there is no significant difference in the level of effectiveness of online platforms for school heads' professional development when grouped according to varied parameters such as: conferences, trainings and webinars, coaching and mentoring, continuing education, and research. Based on the findings, conclusions were drawn, and recommendations given to assist the future researchers. It is highly recommended that the Department of Education (DepEd) should provide funding support fund for the upgrading of technology skills on online platforms for school heads through training. It should also provide funding support for the procurement of computer or electronic hardware to support the upgrading of technology skills on online platform of school heads. Likewise, it should institutionalize the use of online platforms for wide, fast, and easy information dissemination all throughout its sections. It is also best recommended that School heads should maintain positive perspective and values on learning and employing online platforms and should use these technology skills in daily tasks to achieve technological fluency even without pandemic. More so, they should continuously accept opportunities for their professional development as long as they are serving DepED. The study results calls for Education leaders may come up with innovations utilizing online platforms for School Heads' professional development and future researchers may replicate this study and may use as reference.

Introduction:

School leaders to be as effective as possible, should continually expand their knowledge and skills to implement the best educational practices needed most in implementing programs and projects in school. Professional development is the only strategy school systems must strengthen to improve their performance levels. Moreover, Hulya Senul (2019) stated that there is an increasing demand for schools to demonstrate the progress of their students as twenty-first-century learners. To meet these expectations, schools need a new generation of instructional leaders who can transform schools. Educational leadership influences not only the school's effectiveness but also the performance of students in four pathways as organizational, rational, emotional, and familial. This effect is greater if they focus on teaching and learning. Principals directly affect the academic capacity of schools and influence the growth of students indirectly. Professional development of school principals should continue and be sustainable after they have been appointed to their schools.

However, World Health Organization (WHO) declared the outbreak of a new coronavirus disease, COVID – 19, to be a Public Health Emergency and stated that there is a high risk of COVID- 19 spreading to many countries around the world and assessed it as a pandemic. This crisis generated stress and challenge throughout the population particularly the school heads who are having a difficult time delivering the varied tasks entrusted to them.

This paved way for online professional development opportunities for school heads to cope with the needs in aligning their skills to the new normal system in managing school. This is relatively new in the educational arena (Dede, 2006a), but have been available in the business sector for nearly two decades. Online professional development specifically designed for online professional development is even newer, and little research has been conducted to assess the effectiveness of the utilization of DepED recommended online platforms for professional development programs.

In this regard despite the threat of the pandemic, the Department of Education ensured the continual activity for the professional development of DepED personnel through issuing the Office Memorandum OUA Memo 00-0420-0042 dated April 12, 2020, recommending online platforms to be utilized for video conferencing and other online activities for the professional development of the personnel in the field. This also supports the upskilling and reskilling of personnel in addressing their professional development need in the use of online platforms. However, due to limitations and unfamiliarity of online platforms, some school heads are struggling to participate in activities for their professional development which might result in poor implementation of programs and projects or will be left behind unskilled to cope with their professional development needs.

It was upon this reason that triggered the researcher to investigate the level of effectiveness of DepED's recommended online platforms for the professional development of school heads in the Schools Division of Escalante City.

The findings of this study were therefore beneficial to the school heads and to the Schools Division of Escalante City to assess the effectiveness of these online platforms in their professional development that could help achieve quality management of the school system.

Literature Review:

This section presented a review of related literature and studies relevant to the study investigated. The prime purpose of this study was to have a thorough assessment of the effectiveness and impact of the recommended online platforms for the professional development of school heads in the Division of Escalante City specifically on the following parameters: educational leadership, learning environment, human resource management and development, parents' involvement and community partnerships, and school leadership management and operations. The researcher looked into possible variables that might affect the effectiveness of online platforms on the professional development of school heads such as age, sex, educational attainment, school type/ level, location of the school to reflect on comprehensive findings.

Professional Development of School Heads

According to Hayes Mizell (2010) "professional development," usually mean a formal process such as a conference, seminar, or workshop; collaborative learning among members of a work team; or a course at a college or university. However, professional development can also occur in informal contexts such as discussions among work colleagues, independent reading and research, observations of a colleague's work, or other learning from a peer. More so, people often use other names, including staff development, in-service, training, professional learning, or continuing education. Whatever the term, the purpose is the same — to improve learning for educators and students.

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Furthermore, contemporary professional development teams need to consider how to best provide opportunities that align with a social constructivist paradigm in which learning is accomplished through the construction of knowledge blended with dialogue, relationships, and self-directed learning (Cartner & Hallas, 2017; Saroyan & Trigwell, 2015). It is also stressed that providing opportunities for the building of skills and confidence through the sharing of effective practices can create a system in which the learning and content are individualized and evolve based on participant needs (Dron & Anderson, 2014; Krutka, Carptenter & Trust, 2017; McConnell, et al., 2012). Professional development in this context allows faculty members to share the unique expertise they bring to the learning environment, to learn from each other (Cox, 2012; Trust, Carpenter, & Krutka, 2017), and to better understand the relationship between new learning and enhanced teaching methods (Zhang & Wong, 2018).

Concerning this, Hulya Senol (2019) expressed that the role of educational leaders has been undergoing many changes in the era of globalization due to the diverse needs and expectations of the stakeholders of education. This increases the need for the professional development of educational leaders to fulfill their roles. Educational leaders have a high impact on shaping school culture, school improvement, student learning, and achievement so that their professional development is critical to their continued success as leaders.

Social media as a platform for professional learning can also be used as a mechanism to mitigate challenges with other delivery methods, such as formal courses delivered via a learning management system (LMS). For example, a formal course is often associated with a passive learning role for the participant, as when and how to engage

with peers is usually structured and prescribed. In addition, content is often predetermined with parameters around context. In contrast, a social media platform may provide for an environment that overcomes preconceived perceptions about learner role (Krutka, Carpenter, & Trust, 2017). Advantages of a social media platform for professional learning include that it supports learners in being producers of information rather than passive consumers, promotes the learning through the understanding of others' experiences, and embraces a desire to continue learning with a social community of peers (Sullivan, Neu, & Yang, 2018).

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Bedford (2019) voiced that using Social Media as a Platform for a Virtual Professional Learning Community is effective and gives a positive impact on personnel's performance. In contrast, a social media platform may provide for an environment that overcomes preconceived perceptions about learner role (Krutka, Carpenter, & Trust, 2017). Advantages of a social media platform for professional learning include that it supports learners in being producers of information rather than passive consumers, promotes the learning through the understanding of others' experiences, and embraces a desire to continue learning with a social community of peers (Sullivan, Neu, & Yang, 2018).

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Professional Development of School Heads Amidst Pandemic

Contemporary professional development teams need to consider how to best provide opportunities that align with a social constructivist paradigm in which learning is accomplished through the construction of knowledge blended with dialogue, relationships, and self-directed learning (Cartner & Hallas, 2017; Saroyan & Trigwell, 2015).

Sameer Sampat (2020) articulated that school leaders' roles have been unexpectedly and dramatically changed by the COVID-19 crisis. The unprecedented nature of this situation means there is no set direction for them to follow. School leaders are like actors in a play where the story, the script, and costumes have all changed mid-performance, and they are on stage improvising to adjust to their new role. Very few school leaders have thorough training and support for their role, and even fewer have been given clear guidelines on their expectations through disaster response and recovery. He further added that, despite these daunting circumstances, we have seen incredibly inspiring school leaders acting to ensure the safety and wellbeing of families and minimizing the disruption faced by out-of-school children. It is critical that governments set clear guidelines on what is expected of school leaders and well as providing support and resources required to perform their roles.

School leaders have an important perspective on the challenges faced by their communities, and their voices should be incorporated when defining their role during the crisis. Globally, our school leaders are most concerned with student well-being, online teaching, and finances, and should be upskilled with online professional development.

More so, Nannyonjo, et.al (2020) stated that school leaders bear the primary responsibility of ensuring the well-being of their personnel and students and finding ways to ensure that students are learning while in-school learning is suspended. A survey of over 1,800 leaders across 12 countries found that more than 70% of principals felt that the well-being of students in their school was their primary responsibility. Speaking with education officials from governments in four countries, during a recent webinar hosted by Global School Leaders, it was clear that education systems should be delivering four clear messages to school leaders to improve student well-being and engagement through this crisis and as they move toward reopening schools: Focus on basic needs first, focus on the most marginalized and at-risk children, and focus on engaging the community through communication and collaboration.

A strong response by school leaders is more urgent now than ever before to mitigate the disruption children are facing as they continue to be out of school. Education systems need to empower and support school leaders to focus on student success.

Sampat (2020) also believed that it is important to provide support to leaders to face the challenges to lead through. Moving toward context-specific, online professional development programs is critical support for leaders.

Through our initial online work with school leaders, one lesson we have come to is that a key role for education systems during this time is to connect school leaders in peer groups so that they can rapidly share best practices.

Online Platforms

Anchored on Office Memorandum OUA Memo 00-0420-0042 and Regional Memorandum No. 114, s.2020 the utilization of Microsoft Teams, Workplace by Facebook, and Google meet are strongly recommended to be used by the concerned field personnel of DepEd for videoconferencing and other online activities. It further stipulated that the upskilling and reskilling of the personnel in using these online platforms to address their professional development needs are needed. DepEd has existing arrangements on the said organizations and platforms which ensures that information and video conferences are strictly confidential.

Microsoft Teams

Microsoft Teams is a hub for teamwork, which brings together everything a team needs: chat and threaded conversations, meetings & video conferencing, calling content collaboration with the power of Microsoft 365 applications, and the ability to create and integrate apps and workflows that your business relies on.

Garcia (2016) noted that to bring quality education in far-flung areas that have no electricity or connectivity, the Department of Education (DepEd) has teamed up with Microsoft Philippines in launching the EGG – a self-contained classroom that can be transported to remote areas, generate its water and power system and has internet connectivity.

The EGG can accommodate more than 30 students and can be easily set up within three days and is an innovative approach that addresses the archipelagic nature of our country where delivering education to every nook and cranny is a real challenge.

Ilagan (2018) also stressed that presently is the perfect time to fully harness the power of technology and help Filipino learners get a 21st-century education through connectivity for all and Microsoft is glad to be spearheading this initiative with DepEd.

Workplace by Facebook

Pursuant to DepEd Memorandum (OUA Memo 14-0319-0124) entitled “Validation and Provision of Office 365 Accounts for Regional and Division Office Employees” and based on the previous DepED SIPAG 2019 Workplace Set-up, all employees both teaching and non-teaching (with permanent item) is required to download Facebook Workplace and register using the DepEd Email Account. DepEd Central Office thru the Office of Undersecretary for Administration has created and designed a specific format in registering Facebook Workplace (Llego, 2019).

Workplace is a dedicated and secure space for companies to connect, communicate and collaborate. Organizations of all sizes can use familiar Facebook features such as News Feed, groups, messages, and events to get things done.

Google Meet

With Google Meet, everyone can safely create and join high-quality video meetings for groups of up to 250 people. Meet safely - video meetings are encrypted in transit and our array of safety measures are continuously updated for added protection. It has the following features: host large meetings - invite up to 250 participants to a meeting, whether they're in the same team or outside of your organization; easy access on any device - share a link and invite team members to join your conversations with one click from a web browser. While the Google Meet mobile app has the following features: share your screen - present documents, slides, and more during your conference call; participate in broadcasted events - teams, businesses, and schools can view and present in live-streamed events that include up to 100,000 in-domain viewers; record for later - for important events on your calendar, hit record while in the meeting and get the recording file straight from Google Drive and follow along - live, real-time captions powered by Google.

Synthesis

The literature review outlined and discussed the online platforms and some professional development issues with connections to the study that will be conducted. Through a review of literature, it can be found out theories that support the stand of this study for more comprehensive findings. Sampat (2020) strongly affirms that online platforms are effective in upgrading the professional development of a person. Bedford (2019) also affirm this claim as he voiced that using Social Media as a Platform for a Virtual Professional Learning Community is effective and gives a positive impact on personnel's performance.

Research Questions

This research investigation primarily aimed to measure the level of effectiveness of online platforms in the professional development of school heads of the Schools Division of Escalante City amidst pandemic.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of school heads in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Educational Attainment
 - 1.4 School Level
 - 1.5 Location of School
 - 1.6 Work Experience
2. What is the level of the effectiveness of online platforms in the professional development of school heads of the Schools Division of Escalante City when assessed according to:
 - 2.1 Conferences
 - 2.2 Trainings and Webinars
 - 2.3 Coaching and Mentoring
 - 2.4 Continuing Education
 - 2.5 Research
3. What is the level of the effectiveness of online platforms in the professional development of school heads of the Schools Division of Escalante City when assessed according to: age, sex, educational attainment, school type, location of school and work experience?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of effectiveness of online platforms in the professional development of school heads of Escalante City Division when they are grouped according to age, sex, educational attainment, school type, location of the school, work experience as school head?

Scope and Limitations

This research study intended to determine the level of effectiveness of DepEd's recommended platforms in the professional development of school heads in the Schools Division of Escalante City amidst pandemic.

The analysis of the topics under consideration was grounded on the responses of the respondents to the items in the questionnaire that will be utilized by the researcher. The researcher conducted the survey from January 2021 to the school of the Schools Division of Escalante 41 school heads who are the target respondents.

Research Methodology

This section presented the sampling method, data collection, ethical issues, and plan for data analysis of the research study. This study applied a descriptive method of research using a survey questionnaire.

Sampling

To determine the school heads of the Division of Escalante City, total enumeration was used. This means that all 27 Elementary School Heads and 14 Secondary School Heads a total of 41 respondents were the actual subjects of the study.

Data Collection Method

The researcher utilized a survey questionnaire which consists of two main parts namely:

Part I of the research instrument determined the profile of school heads in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, school type, and school location.

Part II of the instrument was a rating scale on the level of effectiveness of online platforms on the professional development of school heads amidst pandemic.

To test the validity of the instrument, content validity was used. The instrument was presented to the top three (3) master's degree holder jurors for them to go over the items comprehensively and will judge the suitability and appropriateness of the questions. Recommendations and suggestions for the improvement of the data gathering instrument were taken into consideration. Each juror was requested to analyze and rate the questionnaire based on criteria presented by Cater V. Good and Douglas H. Scates. Validity index was 3.89 which indicates high degree of validity.

Reliability validation of the instrument was also established by utilizing inter-rater reliability statistics. Reliability result proved that the instrument was reliable with Cohens Alpha value .966 which indicates high strength of agreement.

In the conduct of this study, permission from the respective authorities was requested by the researcher for the administration of the research instrument to the target respondents.

Upon the permit was granted, the researcher will reproduce enough copies of the questionnaire and will administer it to the target respondents. The researcher ensured that every participant that will participate is encouraged to answer the survey questionnaire openly and honestly. Confidentiality of the results and anonymity of the participants were given utmost consideration.

After the conduct of the instrument, questionnaires were retrieved and data were tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted according to the specific problems outlined in this study.

Data Analysis Plan

In interpreting the data, the researcher employed descriptive statistics. To answer the research question in determine the respondents' profile, frequency and percentages were applied. On the other hand, to determine the level effectiveness of online platforms in the professional development on various areas such as: conferences, trainings and webinars, coaching and mentoring, continuing education and research, of school heads in Escalante City Division, mean and standard deviation were utilized. Finally, to determine the significant difference in the level of effectiveness of online platforms in the professional development of school heads in Schools Division of Escalante City, anova was utilized.

Ethical Issues

The researcher desired to ensure that this study will promote quality research and the data that will be gathered are factual and free from biases. Further, this investigation protected the integrity of the respondents and the data, guard against improper conduct in research, and cope with novel and stimulating complications that will arise as the research progresses.

Thus, the researcher sought consent from all the respondents and individuals who will be participating in this study.

To uphold the confidentiality of the research data, the researcher ensured that questionnaires do not reflect the names of the participants, and all research data were input safely archived. After gathering the data, the names of the respondents were altered and coded to shield their right to anonymity and confidentiality. The privacy and anonymity of the respondents' profiles were guaranteed in this research study.

Discussion of Results and Recommendations

Results/ Findings

Profile of School Heads in Terms of Grouping Variables

As unveiled in Table 1, when grouped according to school heads' age, out of 41 school heads in the Division of Escalante City, 1 or 2.4% is 20-31 years of age, 3 or 7.3% are 31-40 years old, 12 or 29.3% are 41-50 years old and 3 or 7.3% are 61 years old and above. This table further revealed that most of the school heads in the Schools Division of Escalante City could be considered at an old age group. Majority of the school heads are aging 51-60 years old.

Table 1
Profile of School Heads in Terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20-30 years old	1	2.4
31-40 years old	3	7.3
41-50 years old	12	29.3
51-60 years old	22	53.7
61 years old above	3	7.3
Total	41	100%

As displayed in Table 2, when grouped according to sex, out of 41 school heads in the Division of Escalante City, 18 or 43.90% are males and 23 or 56.10% are females. More of the respondents are females but not far to the number of males.

Table 2
Profile of School Heads in Terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	18	43.90%
Female	23	56.10%
Total	41	100.00

As presented in Table 3, when grouped according to educational attainment, out of 41 school heads in the Division of Escalante City, 3 or 7.30% are bachelor's degree achievers, 13 or 31.7% attained master's degree undergraduate, 12 or 29.3% have attained Master's Degree and also 12 achieved Doctorate Degree undergraduate and 1 school head or 2.4% graduated from Doctorate Degree. More of the respondents are females but not far to the number of males. These data revealed that most of school heads in the Division of Escalante City pursued graduate and post graduate studies for professional development. This indicates engagement in learning and acquiring more skills and expertise for continuous professional improvement.

Table 3
Profile of School Heads in Terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelor's degree	3	7.3%
Master's degree Undergraduate	13	31.7%
Master's Degree	12	29.3%
Doctorate Degree Undergraduate	12	29.3%
Doctorate Degree	1	2.4%
Total	41	100%

Table 4 disclosed that, when grouped according to school type, out of 41 schools in the Division of Escalante City, 27 or 65.9% are elementary and 14 or 34.1% are secondary. As to these data, almost half of the number is the difference in the number of elementary from secondary schools.

Table 4
Profile of Schools in Terms of Type

Type	Frequency	Percentage
Elementary	27	65.9%
Secondary	14	34.1%
Total	41	100.00

Table 5 on the other hand divulged that the 41 school heads in the Division of Escalante City manage schools in different type of vicinity. When grouped according to school location, 36 or 87.80% are situated in rural areas and 5 or 12.2% are stationed in urban areas. As to demography majority of the schools in the entire division where sited on rural areas wherein internet signal could be a challenge.

Table 5
Profile of Schools in Terms of Locality

Type	Frequency	Percentage
Rural	36	87.80%
Urban	5	12.20%
Total	41	100.00

As exhibited in Table 6, when grouped according to work experience, out of 41 school heads in the Division of Escalante City, 3 or 7.30% have below 1 year experience in managing schools, 8 or 19.5% are 1-5 years of work experience as school head, 13 or 31.7% have 6-10 years work experience, 10 or 24.4% among them have 11-15 years' experience in school management and 7 or 17.1% have an experience in school management of 20 years and above. These data exposed that most of the school heads in the Schools Division of Escalante are well experienced and seasoned managers in terms of length of service in school operations and management. Yet, it also indicated neophytes in terms school management.

Table 6
Profile of School Heads in Terms of Work Experience

Years of Experience	Frequency	Percentage
Below 1 year	3	7.30%
1-5 years	8	19.50%
6-10 years	13	31.70%
11- 15 years	10	24.40%
20 years and above	7	17.10%
Total	41	100%

In Table 7, it flaunted the level of effectiveness of online platforms in the professional development of school heads in the Schools Division of Escalante City when taken as a whole, garnered a grand mean score 3.9200 which means high. When assessed according to different areas the level of effectiveness of online platforms in the professional development of school heads first focusing on conferences attended is high with the mean score of 4.0878. While on the area of trainings and webinars of school heads, the level of effectiveness of online platforms is 4.1512 which has a descriptive interpretation as high. On coaching and mentoring on the other hand, the effectiveness of online platforms for school heads garnered a mean score of 3.8732 which is also high. For continuing education parameter of professional development of school heads data showed a mean score of 3.5805 which implies high. Lastly, for research part of professional development of school heads data garnered a mean score of 3.9073 which denotes high. These data revealed that among the five areas in the professional development of school heads which in this new normal set up employed online platforms and webinars they obtain the highest level of effectiveness and on continuing education they obtain the lowest mean score.

Table 7
Level of Effectiveness of Online Platforms in the Professional Development of School Heads when Assessed in Diverse Areas

Professional Development Areas Employing Online Platforms	Std. Deviation	Mean	Description
Conferences	.81492	4.0878	High
Trainings and Webinars	.84235	4.1512	High
Coaching and Mentoring	.75598	3.8732	High
Continuing Education	.87385	3.5805	High
Research	.89900	3.9073	High
Grand Mean	0.83722	3.9200	High

Table 8 displayed that the level of effectiveness of online platforms in the professional development of school heads in the Schools Division of Escalante City when assessed according to age is very high on conferences for ages 20-60 years old and high for 61 years old and above school heads. This means that attending conferences utilizing online platforms is effective for all the school heads in Schools Division of Escalante City. For all areas of professional development of school head utilizing online platforms, 20-31-year-old school head attained very high level of effectiveness. More so, data also showed high level of effectiveness to school heads aging 31-40 years old, 41-50 years old, 51-60 years old and 61 years old and above with mean scores 4.1333, 3.7333, 3.9273 and 3.4000, respectively. This data revealed that participating to training and webinars using online platforms is highly effective to school heads and they could be able to enhance their learning and gained updates through these online platforms. On the area of coaching and mentoring, 21-31 years old school head could be able to impart ideas, information, and technical assistance effectively to teachers and fellows using online platforms having a mean score of 5.000 which described as very high level of effectiveness. Those on ages 31-40, 41-50, and 51-60-years old school heads also declared effective manipulation of online platforms in coaching and mentoring their teachers, personnel, and fellows with the means scores 4.000, 3.5167, and 3.5909 which is high level of effectiveness. For 61 years old and above, coaching and mentoring and continuing education using online platforms moderately effective to them. On research area, very high level of effectiveness I utilizing online platforms were noted on ages 21-30 and 31-40 years old and high level of effectiveness for 41-61 years old and above. This exhibited that school heads at any age level continue updating their selves with information and learnings through research.

Table 8
Level of the Effectiveness of Online Platforms in the Professional Development of School Heads of the Schools Division of Escalante City when Assessed According to Age

Professional Development Areas Employing Online Platforms	Age	Std. Deviation	Mean	Description
Conferences	20-30 years old	.	4.6000	Very high
	31-40 years old	.23094	4.5333	Very high
	41-50 years old	1.23387	3.9333	Very high
	51-60 years old	.67047	4.2000	Very high
	61 years old above	.64291	4.1333	High
Trainings and Webinars	20-31 years old	.	5.0000	Very high
	31-40 years old	.11547	4.1333	High
	41-50 years old	1.12600	3.7333	High
	51-60 years old	.52931	3.9273	High
	61 years old above	.52915	3.4000	High
Coaching and Mentoring	20-31 years old	.	5.0000	Very high
	31-40 years old	1.00000	4.0000	High
	41-50 years old	.98888	3.5167	High
	51-60 years old	.76713	3.5909	High
	61 years old above	.80829	2.8667	Moderate
Continuing Education	20-31 years old	.	5.0000	Very high
	31-40 years old	.46188	4.0000	High
	41-50 years old	1.16137	3.5167	High
	51-60 years old	.76526	3.5909	High
	61 years old above	1.00000	2.8667	moderate
Research	20-31 years old	.	5.0000	Very high
	31-40 years old	.46188	4.4667	Very high
	41-50 years old	1.16137	3.6833	High
	51-60 years old	.76526	3.8909	High
	61 years old above	1.00000	4.0000	High

As revealed in Table 9, when assessed according to sex males have lower level of effectiveness in employing online platforms in all areas of the professional development of school head compared to females. Further, data revealed that on conferences, trainings and webinars and research females dominate the males in effectively utilizing the online platforms which is very high level. Both sexes attained their lowest level of effectiveness in utilizing online platforms in continuing education aspect of professional development having the means score of 3.3667 and 3.7478. As a whole, both sexes effectively employed online platforms in their professional development. This data implies that female school heads were better in utilizing online platforms in their professional development compared to males.

Table 9
Level of the Effectiveness of Online Platforms in the Professional Development of School Heads of the Schools Division of Escalante City when Assessed according to Sex

Professional Development Areas Employing Online Platforms	Sex	Std. Deviation	Mean	Description
Conferences	Male	.97317	3.7000	High
	Female	.50625	4.3913	Very High
Trainings and Webinars	Male	1.01704	3.6556	High
	Female	.36399	4.5391	Very high
Coaching and Mentoring	Male	.90178	3.5444	High
	Female	.50311	4.1304	High
Continuing Education	Male	.83525	3.3667	High
	Female	.88465	3.7478	High
Research	Male	.90749	3.4000	High
	Female	.67654	4.3043	Very High

As revealed in Table 10, when assessed according to educational attainment, in the conference aspect the school heads with educational attainment from Masters Undergraduate to Doctorate degree achieved a very high level of effectiveness while those who attained Bachelors degree reached high level of effectiveness in utilizing online platforms on attending conferences. On trainings and webinars area of professional development, the result revealed varying level with those attained Bachelors and Masters and Doctorate Degree achieved very high level while those with Masters Undergraduate and Doctorate Undergraduate Degree attained high level of effectiveness.

On coaching and mentoring area of professional development of school heads, those who attained bachelor's degree and Doctorate Degree garnered very high level of effectiveness in employing online platforms. On the continuing education aspect of professional development of school heads, regardless of educational attainment the results showed high level of effectiveness of online platforms with Doctorate Degree attained the lowest mean score of 3.6000. This means that since reaching this level of attainment is already the topmost level continuing education may not so a priority anymore. However, in research area of professional development the level of effectiveness of online platforms is very high for those with Masters undergraduate and Doctorate Degree while high level to those with Bachelors, Masters and Doctorate Undergraduate Degree. This implies that educational attainment of the school heads does not relatively affect the level of effectiveness of online platforms in their professional development.

Table 10
Level of the Effectiveness of Online Platforms in the Professional Development of School Heads of the Schools Division of Escalante City when Assessed According to Educational Attainment

Professional Development Areas Employing Online Platforms	Educational Attainment	Std. Deviation	Mean	Description
Conferences	Bachelors Degree	.98658	4.1333	High
	Masters Undergraduate	.36162	3.8923	Very High
	Master Degree	.47354	4.4333	Very high
	Doctorate Degree Undergraduate	1.28617	3.9167	High
	Doctorate Degree	.	4.4000	Very High
Trainings and Webinars	Bachelors Degree	.98658	4.3333	Very High
	Masters Undergraduate	.66023	3.9385	High
	Master Degree	.40113	4.5500	Very High
	Doctorate Degree Undergraduate	1.21043	3.9167	High
	Doctorate Degree	.	4.4000	Very High
Coaching and Mentoring	Bachelors Degree	.75719	4.4667	Very High
	Masters Undergraduate	.53875	3.6769	High
	Master Degree	.64644	4.0833	High
	Doctorate Degree Undergraduate	1.00363	3.7000	High
	Doctorate Degree	.	4.2000	Very High
Continuing Education	Bachelors degree	.80829	3.8732	High
	Masters Degree Undergraduate	.85395	3.8667	High
	Master Degree	.89781	3.3385	High
	Doctorate Degree Undergraduate	.88215	3.6333	High
	Doctorate Degree	.	3.6000	High
Research	Bachelors Degree	.94516	4.0667	High
	Masters Undergraduate	.76661	3.6462	Very High
	Master Degree	.81557	4.1833	High
	Doctorate Degree Undergraduate	1.13498	3.8500	High
	Doctorate Degree	.	4.2000	Very High

As disclosed in Table 11, when assessed according to location of school the level of effectiveness of online platforms in the professional development of school heads significantly those who are in the schools located in urban areas made to a very high level of effectiveness in participating in trainings and webinars with a mean score of 4.4400 while those on rural areas reached a mean score of 4.1111 which means high level. This implies that the proximity of the schools in the city proper where internet signal is more stable gives opportunity to school heads to attend to trainings and webinars utilizing online platforms due to the current pandemic. For those areas of professional development of school heads on conferences, coaching and mentoring and continuing education and research were all in high level of effectiveness. Further, for school heads whose schools located on rural areas declared that among the areas of professional development, in continuing education they attained the lowest level of effectiveness in online platforms with the mean score of 3.5222 and on trainings and webinars they attained the highest level of effectiveness with the mean score of 4.111. On the other hand, those school heads assigned to schools in urban areas got a lowest level of effectiveness of online platforms in research with a mean score of 3.7600 and highest level of effectiveness of online platforms on trainings and webinars with a mean score of

4.4400. This implies that school location affects the level of effectiveness of utilizing online platforms in the professional development of school heads.

Table 11
Level of the Effectiveness of Online Platforms in the Professional Development of School Heads of the Schools Division of Escalante City when Assessed According to Location of the School

Professional Development Areas Employing Online Platforms	Location	Std. Deviation	Mean	Description
Conferences	Rural	.86106	4.0833	High
	Urban	.38987	4.1200	High
Trainings and Webinars	Rural	.88472	4.1111	High
	Urban	.35777	4.4400	Very High
Coaching and Mentoring	Rural	.80339	3.8500	High
	Urban	.16733	4.0400	High
Continuing Education	Rural	.87672	3.5222	High
	Urban	.81240	4.0000	High
Research	Rural	.94434	3.9278	High
	Urban	.49800	3.7600	High

As unveiled in Table 12, when assessed according to the type of school, the school heads in elementary level attained very high level of effectiveness in manipulating online platforms in attending conferences with the mean score of 4.2148 and on participating in trainings and webinars with the mean score of 4.2815. It could be viewed in the data that in conferences, trainings and webinars, coaching and mentoring and research areas of professional development elementary school heads lead the mean scores compared with the secondary school heads. Only in continuing education of professional development where the secondary school heads gained the higher level of effectiveness of online platforms with the mean score of 3.8571. As a whole, this implies that, elementary school heads are more effective in employing online platforms on conferences, trainings and webinars, coaching and mentoring and research than secondary school heads but not in continuing education.

Table 12
Level of the Effectiveness of Online Platforms in the Professional Development of School Heads of the Schools Division of Escalante City when Assessed According to Type of School

Professional Development Areas Employing Online Platforms	School type	Std. Deviation	Mean	Description
Conferences	Elementary	.59466	4.2148	Very High
	Secondary	1.11266	3.8429	High
Trainings and Webinars	Elementary	.52990	4.2815	Very High
	Secondary	1.23226	3.9000	High
Coaching and Mentoring	Elementary	.58393	3.9407	High
	Secondary	1.02411	3.7429	High
Continuing Education	Elementary	.86298	3.4370	High
	Secondary	.85729	3.8571	High
Research	Elementary	.78214	3.9407	High
	Secondary	1.12093	3.8429	High

As unveiled in Table 13, there is no significant difference in the level of effectiveness of online platforms in the professional development of school heads when assessed according to age. As indicated in the table, for each area for professional development the age bracket of 20-31 years old gained the highest mean score starting from conference, which is 4.6000, trainings and webinars which, coaching and mentoring, continuing education and lastly research which is 5.000. It is followed by school heads with an age bracket of 31-40 years old. Further, continuing education and mentoring and coaching using online platforms are big challenge to 61 years old and above with the mean score of 2.8667. This implies that younger school heads adapt the online platforms to support their professional development more effective compared to those school heads who are older ones. With this, online platforms it is considerable that younger school heads had a little adjustment in enhancing their professional development compared to those school heads who are on their way for retirement where these online platforms became a new learning and adjustment for them to cope for new normal set up.

Table 13
Comparison on the Level of the Effectiveness of Online Platforms in the Professional Development of School Heads of the Schools Division of Escalante City when Assessed According to Age

Professional Development Areas Employing Online Platforms	Age	Std. Dev.	Mean	f-test	p.value	Interpretation
Conferences	20-31 years old	.	4.6000	.792	.538	Not significant
	31-40 years old	.23094	4.5333			
	41-50 years old	1.23387	3.9333			
	51-60 years old	.67047	4.2000			
	61 years old above	.64291	4.1333			
Trainings and Webinars	20-31 years old	.	5.0000	.419	.794	Not significant
	31-40 years old	.11547	4.1333			
	41-50 years old	1.12600	3.7333			
	51-60 years old	.52931	3.9273			
	61 years old above	.52915	3.4000			
Coaching and Mentoring	20-31 years old	.	5.0000	1.077	.382	Not significant
	31-40 years old	1.00000	4.0000			
	41-50 years old	.98888	3.5167			
	51-60 years old	.76713	3.5909			
	61 years old above	.80829	2.8667			
Continuing Education	20-31 years old	.	5.0000	1.404	.252	Not significant
	31-40 years old	.46188	4.0000			
	41-50 years old	1.16137	3.5167			
	51-60 years old	.76526	3.5909			
	61 years old above	1.00000	2.8667			
Research	20-31 years old	.	5.0000	.842	.508	Not significant
	31-40 years old	.46188	4.4667			
	41-50 years old	1.16137	3.6833			
	51-60 years old	.76526	3.8909			
	61 years old above	1.00000	4.0000			

Table 14 pointed that there is no significant difference in the level of effectiveness of online platforms in the professional development of school heads when assessed according to sex. As disclosed in the table, for each area for professional development the females obtained higher mean score than the boys however the difference of these numbers are insignificant which means that the level of effectiveness on online platforms for their professional development of both sexes could not be far from each other and only differs in some insignificant points. It is also exposed in the table that data shows that females gained highest level of effectiveness on online platforms on training and webinars with the mean score of 4.5391 and gained their lowest level of effectiveness on continuing education with mean score of 3.7478. This trend of also true to the males having trainings and webinars had their highest level of effectiveness of online platforms in all areas of professional development with the mean score of 3.6556 and continuing education as the lowest level of effectiveness of online platforms with the mean score of 3.3667.

This implies that online platforms are effective for males and females school head in supporting their professional development though it varies in an insignificant number and in various areas of professional development.

Table 14
Comparison on the Level of Effectiveness of Online Platforms in the Professional Development of School Heads of the Schools Division of Escalante City when Assessed According to Sex

Professional Development Areas Employing Online Platforms	Sex	Std. Deviation	Mean	t-test	p. value	Interpretation
Conferences	Male	.97317	3.7000	1.403	.169	Not significant
	Female	.50625	4.3913			
Trainings and Webinars	Male	1.01704	3.6556	1.391	.172	Not significant
	Female	.36399	4.5391			
Coaching and Mentoring	Male	.90178	3.5444	.791	.434	Not significant
	Female	.50311	4.1304			
Continuing Education	Male	.83525	3.3667	-1.481	.147	Not significant
	Female	.88465	3.7478			

Research	Male	.90749	3.4000	.327	.745	Not significant
	Female	.67654	4.3043			

Table 15 pointed that there is no significant difference in the level of effectiveness of online platforms in the professional development of school heads when assessed according to educational attainment. As disclosed in the table, the level of effectiveness of online platforms in each area of professional development varies insignificantly considering of the educational attainment of the school heads. The table exhibited that for those who have Bachelors degree the highest level of effectiveness of online platforms to them is on coaching and mentoring with the mean score of 4.4667 and the lowest is continuing education with mean score of 3.8732. On those with Masters undergraduate degree the highest level of effectiveness of online platforms is on trainings and webinars with a mean score of 3.9385 and the lowest is on research with the mean score of 3.6462. On the other hand, those with Masters degree gained the highest level of effectiveness in online platforms on trainings and webinars with a mean score of 4.5500 and lowest level of effectiveness on continuing education which garnered a mean score of 3.3385. For doctorate degree undergraduate, the highest level of effectiveness is on trainings and webinars with a mean score of 3.9167 and the lowest is on 3.6333. Lastly, those with doctorate degree, the highest level of effectiveness of online platforms is on trainings and webinars and conferences with a mean score of 4.4000 and the lowest is on continuing education with a mean score of 3.6000.

All in all, as assessed according to educational attainment continuing education is the area in the professional development of school heads which mostly received lowest level of effectiveness of online platforms based on the data presented on the table and highest level of effectiveness of online platforms is on trainings and webinars.

This implies that the level of effectiveness of online platforms for professional development of school heads insignificantly varies with their educational attainment. As assessed, regardless of educational attainment school heads could be able to cope with online platforms for their professional development.

Table 15
Comparison on the Level of Effectiveness of Online Platforms in the Professional Development of School Heads of the Schools Division of Escalante City when Assessed According to Educational Attainment

Professional Development Areas Employing Online Platforms	Educational Attainment	Std. Deviation	Mean	f-test	p. value	Interpretation
Conferences	Bachelors Degree	.98658	4.1333	.888	.481	Not significant
	Masters Under Graduate	.36162	3.8923			
	Masters Degree	.47354	4.4333			
	Doctorate Undergraduate	1.28617	3.9167			
	Doctorate Degree	.	4.4000			
Trainings and Webinars	Bachelors Degree	.98658	4.3333	1.192	.331	Not significant
	Masters Under Graduate	.66023	3.9385			
	Master Degree	.40113	4.5500			
	Doctorate Undergraduate	1.21043	3.9167			
	Doctorate Degree	.	4.4000			
Coaching and Mentoring	Bachelors Degree	.75719	4.4667	1.132	.357	Not significant
	Masters Under Graduate	.53875	3.6769			
	Master Degree	.64644	4.0833			
	Doctorate Undergraduate	1.00363	3.7000			
	Doctorate Degree	.	4.2000			
Continuing Education	Bachelor Degree	.80829	3.8732	1.002	.419	Not significant
	Masters Under Graduate	.85395	3.8667			
	Master Degree	.89781	3.3385			
	Doctorate Undergraduate	.88215	3.6333			
	Doctorate Degree	.	3.6000			
Research	Bachelor Degree	.94516	4.0667	.594	.669	Not significant
	Masters Under Graduate	.76661	3.6462			

	Graduate					
	Master Degree	.81557	4.1833			
	Doctorate	1.1349	3.8500			
	Undergraduate	8				
	Doctorate Degree	.	4.2000			

As presented in Table 16, there is no significant difference in the level of effectiveness of online platforms in the professional development of school heads when assessed according to school's location. As mounted in the table, school heads assigned to schools located in urban areas have higher level of effectiveness of online platforms for their professional development on conferences with a mean score of 4.1200, trainings and webinars with a mean score of 4.4400, coaching and mentoring with a mean score of 4.0400 and in continuing education with a mean score of 4.0000 compared to those school heads assigned to school in rural areas. However, on rural areas research is really needed and the effectiveness of online platforms to them is more significant as shown in the mean score of 3.9278 compared to the schools in the urban areas having a mean a score of 3.7600. However, though there is a difference in the scores but still the difference is insignificant.

This simply implies that school heads assigned in the urban areas gauged higher effectiveness of online platforms in their professional development compared to those on rural areas due to access to stable internet signal. Further, the nearer the proximity of the school to the city the more access to online activities which can contribute to the professional development of the school heads.

Table 16
Comparison on the Level of Effectiveness of Online Platforms in the Professional Development of School Heads of the Schools Division of Escalante City when Assessed According to Location of the School

Professional Development Areas Employing Online Platforms	Location	Std. Deviation	Mean	t-test	p.value	Interpretation
Conferences	Rural	.86106	4.0833	-.093	.926	Not significant
	Urban	.38987	4.1200			
Trainings and Webinars	Rural	.88472	4.1111	-.815	.420	Not significant
	Urban	.35777	4.4400			
Coaching and Mentoring	Rural	.80339	3.8500	-.522	.605	Not significant
	Urban	.16733	4.0400			
Continuing Education	Rural	.87672	3.5222	1.239	.224	Not significant
	Urban	.81240	4.0000			
Research	Rural	.94434	3.9278	-1.220	.701	Not significant
	Urban	.49800	3.7600			

As stated in Table 17, there is no significant difference in the level of effectiveness of online platforms in the professional development of school heads when assessed according to the type of school. As displayed in the table, school heads on elementary schools have higher level of effectiveness of online platforms on conferences, trainings and webinars, coaching and mentoring and research areas of professional development compared to secondary school principals. However, secondary school principals gave a higher level of effectiveness of online platforms on continuing education compared to elementary school principals with the mean scores of 3.8571 and 3.4370, respectively.

This simply implies that school heads in elementary schools have utilized online platforms more effectively than the secondary school heads on conferences, trainings and webinars, coaching and mentoring and research. However, on continuing education, it is the secondary school heads who utilized online platforms more effective.

Table 17
Comparison on the Level of the Effectiveness of Online Platforms in the Professional Development of School Heads of the Schools Division of Escalante City when Assessed According to Type of School

Professional Development Areas Employing Online Platforms	Type of school	Std. Deviation	Mean	t-test	p.value	Interpretation
Conferences	Elementary	.59466	4.2148	1.403	.169	Not significant
	Secondary	1.11266	3.8429			
Trainings and Webinars	Elementary	.52990	4.2815	1.391	.172	Not significant
	Secondary	1.23226	3.9000			
Coaching and Mentoring	Elementary	.58393	3.9407	.791	.434	Not significant
	Secondary	1.02411	3.7429			

Continuing Education	Elementary	.86298	3.4370	-1.481	.149	Not significant
	Secondary	.85729	3.8571			
Research	Elementary	.78214	3.9407	.327	.773	Not significant
	Secondary	1.12093	3.8429			

Based on the results of the study, the following findings were found:

1. On the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Sex. Majority of the respondents of the study are females.
 - 1.2. Age. Based on the presented data, majority of the school heads in the Schools Division of Escalante City are 51-60 years old.
 - 1.3. Educational Attainment. It is found out that most of the school heads have Masters Undergraduate degree, Masters Degree and Doctorate Undergraduate Degree.
 - 1.4. Work Experience as School Head. Most of the respondents in this research have 0-15 years of experience as School Head.
 - 1.5. School Location. Most of the schools in the Schools Division of Escalante City are located at rural areas.
 - 1.6. School Level. Majority of the schools are elementary level.
2. On the level of effectiveness of online platforms for school heads' professional development when assess according to parameters:
 - 2.1. Conferences. The level of effectiveness of online platforms for school heads' professional development on conferences is high.
 - 2.2. Trainings and Webinars. The level of effectiveness of online platforms for school heads' professional development on trainings and webinars is high.
 - 2.3. Coaching and Mentoring. The level of effectiveness of online platforms for school heads' professional development on coaching and mentoring is high.
 - 2.4. Continuing Education. The level of effectiveness of online platforms for school heads' professional development on continuing education is high.
 - 2.5. Research. The level of effectiveness of online platforms for school heads' professional development on research is high.

As a whole, the level of effectiveness of online platforms for school heads' professional development in Schools Division of Escalante City is high.

3. Differences on the effectiveness of online platforms when assessed according to:
 - 3.1. Sex. In conferences, trainings and webinars, coaching and mentoring, continuing education, and research the result showed no significant differences.
 - 3.2. Age. For age as variable, in conferences, trainings and webinars, coaching and mentoring, continuing education, and research the result showed not significant.
 - 3.3. Educational attainment. In this variable, the difference of conferences, trainings and webinars, coaching and mentoring, continuing education, and research the result showed not significant.
 - 3.4. Work Experience as School Head. Taken this, the difference in conferences, trainings and webinars, coaching and mentoring, continuing education, and research the result showed not significant.
 - 3.5. School Location. With this, the difference in conferences, trainings and webinars, coaching and mentoring, continuing education, and research the result showed not significant.
 - 3.6. School Level. With this variable, the difference in conferences, trainings and webinars, coaching and mentoring, continuing education, and research the result showed not significant.

Summary

Results of the study revealed that there is a high level of effectiveness of online platforms on all areas of professional development of school heads such as: conferences, trainings and webinars, coaching and mentoring, continuing education and research. Online platforms were effectively utilized on the five areas of professional development of school heads in the division.

Furthermore, the school heads in the Schools Division of Escalante City had abled to cope and utilized online platforms effectively for their professional development amidst the pandemic. Factors such as sex, age, educational attainment, work experiences, school location and school level aided to give variation on the data but all in all the level of effectiveness of online platforms is highly effective for continuing professional development of school heads. Online platforms supported and helped the school heads continuously acquired substantial learning and enhanced their skills in their field of work and prevent stagnation on their professional progress in the time of pandemic.

Conclusions

Given the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The level of effectiveness of online platforms in the professional development of School Heads in Escalante City Division is highly effective on all areas or parameters.
2. School heads had managed to attend and conduct virtual conferences and orientations for staff development of their respective schools and enabled to acquire professional development resources through different online platforms.
3. School heads coped to participate in webinars and virtual trainings and effectively used online platforms to learn and share their ideas and learnings.
4. School heads exposed themselves in manipulating technology and varied online platforms effectively to cope with new normal set up particularly in extending coaching and mentoring to their fellows, personnel and in accomplishing their tasks.
5. With the new normal set up, school heads effectively managed to attend their graduate and post graduate studies and short courses using online platforms to obtain substantial learning for their professional growth.
6. School heads find online platforms were effective in their professional growth and economical.
7. Due to pandemic, strict health protocols and as based on their needs, school heads had effectively used online platforms to update themselves on policies, directives, mechanisms, and updates on new normal set up.
8. Hence, the researcher concludes that employing online platforms is a huge support and aid on continuing professional development of school heads in the time of pandemic.

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing findings conclusions of the study, the researcher recommended the following:

1. Department of Education (DepEd) should provide funding support fund for the upskilling of technology skills on online platforms for school heads through training.
2. Department of Education (DepEd) should provide funding support for the procurement of computer or electronic hardware to support the upgrading of technology skills on online platform of school heads.
3. Department of Education (DepEd) shall institutionalize the use of online platforms for wide, fast, and easy information dissemination all throughout its sections.
4. School heads should maintain positive perspective and values on learning and employing online platforms and should use these technology skills in daily tasks to achieve technological fluency even without pandemic.
5. School heads should continuously accept opportunities for their professional development as long as they are serving DepED.
6. Education leaders may come up with innovations utilizing online platforms for School Heads' professional development.
7. Future researchers may replicate this study and may use as references.

Plans for Dissemination

The result of this investigation will determine the effectiveness of online platforms to help support and enhance professional development of school heads. Further, the findings of this study, will contribute insights to the Division leaders to support the needs of the school heads in employing online platforms effectively for their professional development. More so, the result of the study will be communicated to the respondents, Division authorities, research conferences and other interested authorities in which this investigation will be worthwhile and for suitable. The confidentiality of the result will be an utmost consideration. Finally, this result of this research will also be disseminated for possible utilization of the data gathered bases for decision and policy making of the agency if found suitable and relevant.

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